

1 The Case for Data Provenance and Authenticity in Genomics

2 Building Trustworthy Foundations for Digital Biology

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6 Abstract

7 The exponential growth of publicly accessible genomic data over the last two decades has
8 transformed life sciences, yet it has also exposed a critical vulnerability. Weakly enforced
9 requirements for data provenance, structured metadata, and material authentication have
10 degraded the potential of these resources for interoperability and reuse in digital biology. The
11 lack of traceability and verification in genomic data poses escalating risks to scientific
12 reproducibility, biosecurity, and the integrity of AI-driven biological research (AIxBio).
13 Examples from cancer and microbial genomics, infectious disease surveillance, public
14 sequence archives, and emerging AI-enabled biology demonstrate how poor data
15 provenance and metadata quality gaps undermine trust, drive irreproducible results, and
16 create opportunities for data fabrication and misuse. The manuscript further emphasizes
17 that reproducibility alone is insufficient when shared reference data are contaminated,
18 mislabeled, incompletely described, or biologically outdated. Furthermore, the unique role
19 of biological repositories and international culture collections is presented as bridging the
20 physical-to-digital divide and enabling the creation of trusted “digital twins” for biological
21 research. Finally, the proactive preservation of physical reference materials underpinning
22 genomic data and an emphasis on “metadata as infrastructure” is presented as a key
23 ingredient for the future success and sustainability of artificial intelligence and machine
24 learning across the life sciences.

25 Introduction

26 Genomic data have become a cornerstone of modern life sciences research, supporting
27 applications that range from tracking infectious disease outbreaks to developing precision
28 diagnostics, engineering new biotechnologies, and advancing our understanding of human
29 health. Since the creation of the Los Alamos Sequence Data Bank in 1979 (1) and the
30 National Institutes of Health GenBank database in 1982 (2), the amount of DNA sequence
31 data available to the global research community has roughly doubled every 24 months (3).
32 This rapid expansion has vastly democratized access to genomic information and fueled

33 countless discoveries. However, it has also exposed a critical weakness in our scientific
34 infrastructure: the lack of robust requirements for data provenance and authenticity in
35 genomic databases. As a result, downstream applications that depend on accurate
36 metadata and sample traceability increasingly face significant challenges in interoperability
37 and reproducibility (4–7).

38 Walter Goad’s 1979 proposal to create the Los Alamos DNA Data Bank acknowledged that
39 the credibility of sequence records could not rest solely on community trust, proposing
40 instead that such a database should include a graded “validation status” tied to objective
41 supporting evidence and independent confirmation (1). In this framework, the provenance
42 of the data, including the methods used to produce it and the source of the original
43 materials, was treated as an artifact equal in importance to the DNA sequence data itself.
44 When the NIH took over management of the Los Alamos data repository and created
45 GenBank in 1982, the NIH ended the practice of assigning a “validation status” for DNA
46 sequence data deposited into the database. Over 40 years later, the primary international
47 sequence repositories (i.e., the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
48 [INSDC], which includes GenBank, the European Nucleotide Archive [ENA], and the DNA
49 Data Bank of Japan [DDBJ]) no longer verify the accuracy or source of the sequences they
50 host. Instead, they operate under a shared model in which the responsibility for record
51 quality and accuracy rests primarily with the submitting author, rather than the database
52 itself (8). Accordingly, INSDC databases function primarily as data archives, not curated
53 repositories of validated reference data. Arguably, given the scale of these databases and
54 the pace at which data are deposited into them, the role of INSDC member databases
55 should not be to “police” the veracity of all data being submitted for distribution, but rather
56 to enable equitable, open, international access to the genomic data for all organisms.

57 Nonetheless, each member database has implemented some level of automated screening
58 to ensure that minimum quality requirements are met for each new submission (9). In
59 practice, data are accepted into INSDC databases without independent authentication or
60 “validation,” and there is no requirement for reference specimens or source materials to be
61 preserved or identified. Notably, the primary metadata standard used by INSDC member
62 databases—the Minimum Information About Any (X) Sample (MIxS)—treats references for
63 biomaterials (ref_biomaterial) and source material identifiers (source_mat_id) as optional or
64 recommended fields (10–12). Thus, provenance (e.g., the documented origin and history of
65 the data) and authenticity (e.g., confidence that data are genuine and untampered) are
66 largely taken on trust. Unfortunately, while the genomics community generally operates
67 under the assumption that most researchers submit correct, well-documented sequences
68 with clear sample (i.e., BioSample) metadata, this assumption is proving increasingly
69 problematic (4–6, 13–16).

70 The absence of enforced data provenance and authenticity standards for both biological
71 materials and experimental methods has led to the widespread practice of researchers
72 contributing only the minimum information needed for each submission. Researchers
73 worldwide deposit genomic data and associated metadata with varying degrees of quality
74 control, often using inconsistent nomenclature and metadata formatting conventions. As
75 expected, human-in-the-loop curation of these databases has not kept pace with their
76 explosive growth. As a result, deposited data are rarely updated or corrected after
77 submission, and the aggregate quality of sample and experimental metadata has degraded
78 over time. Third-party curation and annotation systems, which have been proposed as
79 solutions to this issue (17), have urged NCBI to allow a community-curated annotation
80 process where domain experts could add or correct annotations on sequences.
81 Unfortunately, this proposal was not embraced by INSDC member databases, and NCBI's
82 own limited implementation—the Third Party Annotation [TPA] system—was retired in 2025,
83 reportedly due to excessive technical complexity (18). As a result, public genomics
84 repositories contain large numbers of entries that are incomplete (19–22), mislabeled (23,
85 24), of poor quality (25, 26), or outright fraudulent (27, 28). This significant but
86 underappreciated problem is likely the result of a combination of insufficient minimum
87 requirements for depositing data, poor scientific rigor, and in some cases intentional
88 misconduct or obfuscation. Collectively, these deficiencies impact scientific reproducibility
89 (7, 29–32), public health (5, 33, 34), and biosecurity (35–37).

90 Below, this manuscript reviews the specific issues surrounding the reuse, authentication,
91 and provenance of genomic data, especially as they relate to descriptors for source
92 materials, sample handling, chain of custody, sample processing, and bioinformatics
93 methods. This work closes by arguing that the genomics community does not need to
94 reinvent provenance standards, but must enforce and operationalize existing standards
95 more consistently, preserve physical reference materials where possible, and prioritize
96 targeted retrospective curation of high-value legacy records, especially those used as
97 references, in clinical or regulatory contexts, or in widely reused AI/ML training and
98 benchmark datasets.

99 Missing or Mislabeled Sample Metadata

100 A significant challenge in public genomic repositories is the pervasive lack of essential
101 sample metadata, which are critical for interpreting and integrating genomic sequences
102 across nearly all potential downstream application areas. For pathogen genomics data,
103 these gaps create real-world risks for public health and biosecurity. For example, a 2021 U.S.
104 FDA-led study highlighted how key fields like collection date, geographic origin, host, and
105 other contextual details are widely absent or incomplete in GenBank's BioSample and

106 GenomeTrakr pathogen surveillance databases, largely because MixS guidelines make
107 inclusion of this information optional at the point of submission (5). Their analysis of
108 *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Listeria* genomes found that of the 550,270 genome
109 assemblies inspected, ~25% of the entries were missing at least one crucial piece of
110 metadata needed for public health surveillance and epidemiology. Furthermore, there was
111 a significant disparity between samples identified as “clinical” vs. those from food or
112 environmental sources: clinical samples were missing these metadata in 134,133 (~49%) of
113 the records, whereas only 1,823 samples (0.7%) originating from food and environmental
114 surveillance efforts had missing data. This suggests a meaningful disparity in awareness in
115 the importance of these data among professionals operating in clinical laboratories and
116 highlights an opportunity to improve training for scientists responsible for data collection
117 and submission.

118 Our own analyses of publicly available bacterial genome assemblies also revealed
119 significant metadata deficiencies (38). We examined 2,701 bacterial RefSeq genome
120 assemblies labeled as “ATCC” reference strains and found that nearly half were missing one
121 or more crucial metadata fields (or contained non-informative values) describing how the
122 data were produced and processed. Furthermore, ~40% of records failed to report the
123 sequencing technology or bioinformatics methods used to generate the assembly, and over
124 99% lacked any “isolate” description or source information associated with the originating
125 BioSample. Even the “relation to type material” field (which indicates if a sequence comes
126 from an official bacterial type strain) was empty in 38% of cases, making it difficult to discern
127 whether a given genome sequence corresponds to the canonical type strain reference
128 material for a species or instead represents a derivative, unverified laboratory strain labeled
129 with the same strain name. In addition, among the assemblies examined that were
130 generated from ATCC reference strains, internal ATCC records indicated that only ~15% of
131 sequencing laboratories had obtained the organism directly from ATCC’s culture collection.
132 The remaining ~85% presumably sequenced lab-to-lab clones or derivatives obtained
133 through informal strain sharing between laboratories, a practice that effectively erodes one
134 of the core purposes of international culture collections—namely, serving as a central
135 controlled source of materials (39–41).

136 Similarly for eukaryotic data, a 2021 study by Buckner et al. (4) found that the majority of
137 eukaryotic genetic sequences in GenBank are not linked to any preserved voucher specimen
138 or culture collection record, despite prior calls to address this gap (42). The authors
139 identified a lack of physical traceability, errors in source material information, and the
140 absence of clear descriptions on how the data were produced as collectively posing a
141 “serious impediment” for researchers seeking to confirm that a DNA sequence truly
142 corresponds to the species or strain. They provide cautionary examples in which mislabeled

143 or contaminated sequences entered public databases and remain uncorrected, misleading
144 research until errors are uncovered either unexpectedly or through labor-intensive forensic
145 analyses (43). More recently, Crandall et al. (21) also found that most (87%) genome-scale
146 genetic diversity data in GenBank lack the spatiotemporal metadata needed for reuse.
147 Crandall’s “datathon” further demonstrated a persistent issue: even when metadata can be
148 recovered, it often requires substantial effort involving manual curation due to gaps in data
149 formatting and structure. Moreover, metadata recoverability declines rapidly with age
150 (~13.5% loss per year), reinforcing the need to capture and curate metadata at the point of
151 submission rather than attempting to “fix it later.” These critiques are also consistent with
152 findings from Toczydlowski et al. who found, among more than 300,000 BioSamples tied to
153 Sequence Read Archive (SRA) records relevant to biodiversity research, only ~13% include
154 time and location information, substantially hampering the reuse of these data at scale (20).

155 Unfortunately, missing or incomplete metadata issues are not confined to genomic
156 reference sequences but also significantly affect other important genomics databases such
157 as NCBI’s Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) data repository. In 2025, Huang et al. (22)
158 systematically assessed how missing and inconsistently shared metadata in GEO
159 undermine data reuse and reproducibility: across 253 studies (>164,000 samples) they
160 found that ~25% of critical metadata were omitted, significantly hampering comparative
161 analyses across studies. Furthermore, only 11.5% of these studies fully shared the assessed
162 phenotypes, meaning most records lack the basic descriptors needed to interpret datasets
163 or match samples across studies. The authors explicitly note that metadata fields for
164 sample source (and other similar contextual fields) were often missing or inconsistently
165 reported in both SRA and GEO, thereby limiting reusability even when raw data are
166 deposited.

167 Another study reached a similar conclusion for microbiome-oriented INSDC deposits:
168 despite broad awareness and uptake of MIxS, metadata associated with most samples
169 remained poorly standardized, nonstandard fields introduced substantial variation, and
170 harmonization across studies was often difficult or impossible without manual curation (44).
171 This issue further exacerbates challenges in downstream analytics, including machine
172 learning and AI applications, revealing fundamental shortcomings in how bioinformatics
173 provenance is captured, structured, and maintained.

174 **Bioinformatics Provenance Gaps**

175 Although NCBI repositories such as SRA, BioSample, and GenBank implement structured
176 submission schemas—and in some domains incorporate community standards such as
177 MIxS—these frameworks still capture only a subset of the methodological record. In SRA,

178 technical metadata are organized around the STUDY, SAMPLE, EXPERIMENT, and RUN
179 objects; the EXPERIMENT and RUN records capture items such as library preparation,
180 sequencing strategy, layout, and instrument model (45). However, NCBI also states that
181 most descriptive information is captured at the EXPERIMENT level and depends on
182 submitter-provided Title and Description text. BioSample likewise maintains recognized
183 attributes and package structures but explicitly permits submitters to provide any number
184 of custom attributes. GenBank genome submissions require a limited set of assembly
185 metadata, including assembly method, program version or date, approximate coverage, and
186 sequencing technology, while other informative details such as polishing method or
187 reference-guided status remain optional. Taken together, these repository schemas provide
188 a scaffold for deposition, but they do not constitute a single, consistently enforced,
189 machine-readable standard for end-to-end sequencing and bioinformatics provenance.

190 This limitation is not merely theoretical. A 2015 study examined SRA protocol annotation and
191 found that only ~4% of studies contained annotations for queried preparatory protocol
192 steps, while ~74% of studies had omitted details for those steps; the authors concluded that
193 the current level of annotation inhibits systematic studies of protocol bias and significantly
194 weakens comparative analysis (46). Given the sustained rapid growth of SRA over the last
195 decade, it remains unclear whether any effort has been made to retrospectively improve
196 these metrics for historical samples. At the sample-metadata layer, MetaSRA was
197 developed precisely because SRA-linked BioSample metadata were difficult to use at scale:
198 both property names and values were described as non-standardized and created at the
199 discretion of submitters, resulting in synonyms, misspellings, abbreviations, and free-text
200 phrases that resist large-scale computational reuse (47). Klie and colleagues reported that
201 most SRA samples were missing metadata across several categories and that user-defined
202 fields dominated the metadata landscape. In their dataset, only ~22% of values were paired
203 with BioSample-defined attributes. Another 2019 study found the same pattern in
204 BioSample more broadly: 85% of records used the Generic package, which imposes very few
205 required attributes, and 15% of attribute name-value pairs used *ad hoc* names outside the
206 BioSample dictionary (48). The authors further concluded that most field names and values
207 were not standardized or controlled; many distinct labels were used to represent the same
208 underlying concept, and these inconsistencies impede search and reuse.

209 A central issue across public databases is that metadata are frequently provided only at the
210 experiment level rather than the sample level. The studies cited above emphasize that
211 missing sample-level metadata restricts credibility and can make secondary analysis a
212 substantial challenge (i.e., replication and robust reanalysis require per-sample
213 descriptors). These findings indicate that public archives often preserve raw sequence files

214 more reliably than they preserve the contextual and methodological metadata needed for
215 robust cross-study interpretation, replication, and reuse.

216 The problem becomes even sharper when the focus shifts from sample description to
217 computational provenance. Metadata standards may record platform, library, and
218 assembly-summary fields, but they do not generally require a standardized disclosure of the
219 complete analytical environment: software versions, parameter settings, reference
220 databases, filtering thresholds, contamination-screening logic, branching decisions, or
221 validation procedures (49). This demonstrates why complementary provenance frameworks
222 such as BioCompute are needed as a standard for communicating high-throughput
223 sequencing workflows, validation, and reproducibility (50). Workflow-provenance studies
224 confirm that incomplete documentation of workflow requirements can lead directly to failed
225 re-execution in new environments (51). Therefore, the methodological opacity of public
226 genomics archives is not simply a metadata nuisance; it is a structural trust problem. When
227 sequencing and bioinformatics methods are inconsistently recorded, relegated to free text,
228 or omitted entirely, independent verification becomes harder (and often impossible),
229 comparative reuse becomes more fragile, and the evidentiary value of archived genomic
230 data is weakened. These gaps directly shape whether genomic analyses can be reproduced,
231 meaningfully reanalyzed, or trusted as evidence

232 Scientific Misconduct and Data Fabrication

233 Scientific fraud, including data fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism, should be of
234 significant concern for anyone working in the genomics, bioinformatics, genetics, AlxBio, or
235 digital biology space—especially those working with data sourced from public data
236 repositories. Unfortunately, however, a high degree of presumed trust is placed in data
237 sourced from these databases, despite ample signs that these data should be treated with
238 caution. While most scientists are honest, surveys and meta-analyses indicate a non-trivial
239 minority engage in unethical practices that collectively create significant risks for the entire
240 global genomics research community. A large-scale systematic survey and meta-analysis of
241 prior work on scientific fraud revealed ~2% of scientists in the U.S. and EU admitted to
242 fabricating or falsifying data at least once within the three years prior to being surveyed (52).
243 A subsequent study surveyed 6,813 scientists and found ~4% admitted to fabricating or
244 falsifying existing data one or more times in their careers, largely driven by pressures to
245 publish (53). The problem may be even more widespread: in 2023, an estimated 5.8% of all
246 biomedical research papers published globally were “true fakes” and reported completely
247 fabricated results (54). The issue of fabricated publications has been repeatedly raised by
248 Jennifer Byrne and colleagues, most recently in their analysis of 2.6 million cancer research

249 publications spanning 1999 to 2024 where ~9.9% of all publications were flagged as
250 suspicious and likely originating from “paper mill” publishers (55).

251 Raw genomic data are typically structured as plain-text files (i.e., .fasta, .fastq, .gbk, etc.),
252 making them amenable to computational modeling. As a result, generative approaches for
253 simulating realistic genomic sequence data in silico have been an active area of research in
254 computational biology for decades (56–61). These tools are generally used for
255 benchmarking and testing newly developed bioinformatics algorithms at scale, obviating the
256 need for laboratory experiments. Importantly, however, these same tools can also be used
257 to generate fabricated genomic data or to augment existing datasets with fabricated
258 sequences to deliver a specific result needed for publication. Pairing such datasets with
259 falsified metadata would be trivial. Taken together, these data could be submitted to public
260 genomics databases to support a fabricated publication, which would result in the poisoning
261 of public database integrity and accuracy. Unfortunately, there have been documented
262 instances where falsified genomics data has been found in these databases.

263 The earliest known example of falsified sequencing data associated with peer-reviewed
264 publications occurred in the late 1990s (62). The associated data were later “suppressed”
265 from GenBank after the publications were retracted, but not before being cited 27 times in
266 the literature. In another study, researchers found falsified mitochondrial DNA sequences to
267 support a series of publications and a fabricated phylogenetic tree of sparrow hawks. This
268 was discovered serendipitously after researchers had difficulty identifying the source of
269 voucher specimens for the original (falsified) data and made open calls for improved
270 curation and stronger enforcement of authenticity checks for mitochondrial DNA sequences
271 in public databases (13, 63, 64). Interestingly, these data remain labeled as “UNVERIFIED”
272 in GenBank to this day, leaving the potential for their successful retrieval using common
273 tools like BLAST despite being entirely false. A third example of genomics data misconduct
274 involved falsified and intentionally mislabeled gene expression microarray data put forth as
275 evidence of genomic signatures suitable for companion diagnostics in chemotherapeutics
276 (65). At least two groups independently failed to replicate these results, but the data
277 submitted to GEO were not removed until a third group published a separate peer-reviewed
278 “forensic bioinformatics” publication calling for the retraction of the original paper and data
279 (66). In a fourth case, a scientist falsely claimed successful integration of a therapeutic gene
280 in mice, fabricating DNA sequencing data for CRISPR integration sites and related PCR
281 assays. A 2010 NIH investigation resulted in the retraction of three papers and the
282 cancellation of four grants (67). In a fifth case, DNA methylation sequencing data was
283 falsified by an early-career scientist investigating endocrine disruptors in animal models.
284 After the results could not be replicated, another NIH Office of Research Integrity (ORI)
285 investigation revealed the original results were fabricated, resulting in the retraction of the

286 corresponding paper and removal of the data from public databases (68). Importantly, all
287 the above instances involved discovery of the fabrication only after independent groups
288 attempted to replicate the results, which then triggered investigations once those attempts
289 failed. In all these cases, the removal or suppression of the data did not occur until years
290 after the data were originally deposited and, in some cases, after the original fabricated work
291 was cited by hundreds of separate publications.

292 The examples above represent a small number of readily confirmed cases in which
293 fabricated or falsified genomics or omics data were deposited into public repositories. While
294 the number of documented cases may seem limited, it should be interpreted cautiously
295 given how little systematic work has been directed at detecting fabricated genomic data
296 within public archives. It's also important to consider these findings within the broader
297 context of scientific fraud in general. By the most conservative estimate above, the impact
298 of even 2% of genomics scientists falsifying data would have an enormous detrimental
299 impact on our public data repositories.

300 Very limited research has been directed specifically at detecting fraudulent genomic data
301 that may already exist in INSDC databases (as opposed to published works). Only a single
302 published study has intentionally attempted to detect fraudulent sequencing data directly
303 (69). Ironically, the authors note they were not successful in identifying fraudulent data in
304 GenBank associated with retracted papers, not due to the absence of the data, but instead
305 largely due to gaps in sample and depositor attribution metadata for these data, which made
306 it extremely difficult to properly assess the veracity of data that may be tied to public
307 databases. Separately, Bouadjenek et al. developed a means to assess the quality of
308 sequencing records as a whole (i.e., both the sequence and associated metadata) using a
309 combination of machine learning models and iterative information retrieval strategies (70).
310 They report ~25% of the sequencing records investigated were “suspicious”, although they
311 did not specifically identify these as potentially fabricated and instead frame these as data
312 quality oversights by the submitters. Thus, despite the relative ease with which fabricated
313 genomic data could be produced at scale, the degree to which intentionally falsified data is
314 currently poisoning public databases remains largely unanswered.

315 Reproducible Does Not Mean Correct

316 Irreproducibility is a well-recognized crisis in science, and deficiencies in genomic data
317 quality and metadata completeness materially undermine reproducibility and reuse of
318 genomic data (71–73). The impacts of genomic data contamination (9, 25, 33), incomplete
319 metadata (22, 30, 74), sample-quality imbalance (75), and weak data provenance (38, 51)
320 have been well documented. If published genomic datasets are contaminated, mislabeled,

321 or otherwise unreliable, other scientists may spend extended periods of time chasing false
322 leads or trying and failing to replicate results found in existing published datasets. Worse,
323 they may computationally replicate results from otherwise compromised data and
324 unknowingly reach the same (incorrect) conclusions, a scenario that is often overlooked by
325 early-career scientists who may assume that public datasets are correct (76). Accordingly,
326 the central question is not only whether a genomic result can be reproduced, but whether
327 the data and methods underlying that result are sufficiently authentic, traceable, and well-
328 described to justify confidence in its correctness. Under this model, reproducing prior
329 results then tests both the technical aspects of the replication experiment and the biological
330 validity of the results.

331 Conceptually, reproducibility, replicability, and correctness should not be treated as
332 interchangeable. Reproducibility demonstrates that a result can be regenerated using the
333 same data and analysis; replicability asks whether similar conclusions are obtained when a
334 study is repeated independently; correctness concerns whether the underlying biological
335 claim is true (72, 76). These distinctions matter in genomics because technically
336 reproducible workflows may still yield false biological inferences if the underlying data are
337 contaminated, mislabeled, incompletely described, or interpreted against flawed reference
338 resources. In this sense, reproducibility is necessary for trust, but it is not sufficient.
339 Importantly, archival deposition in repositories such as BioSample, BioProject, GenBank, or
340 SRA should not be mistaken for independent validation. As extensively discussed above,
341 these submitter-driven archives are designed primarily to preserve and disseminate data,
342 not to certify the correctness of the biological claims associated with those data.

343 An additional concern is error propagation through shared databases and analytical
344 infrastructure. Once a contaminated, misclassified, or otherwise defective record enters a
345 public repository, it can be reused in downstream annotation pipelines, comparative
346 genomics studies, taxonomic classifiers, benchmark datasets, meta-analyses, and myriad
347 other reuse cases (73). Subsequent investigators may then obtain concordant results not
348 because the underlying claim is true, but because they are relying on the same compromised
349 inputs. This creates a form of circular confirmation in which “reproducible wrongness” is
350 reinforced by repeated reuse. The problem is amplified by the fact that reference databases
351 themselves are not error-free: large-scale contamination, taxonomic misassignment, and
352 sequence-content errors have all been documented in public sequence resources (23, 26,
353 34, 77). Thus, even technically rigorous analyses may produce stable but incorrect answers
354 when the shared reference layer is flawed.

355 Finally, it is important to recognize that “correctness” in genomics is not a static notion, but
356 a moving target that shifts as scientific understanding advances. However, individual
357 genomics datasets are largely static records that are seldom retrospectively updated or

358 systematically re-analyzed after the data are submitted—even when new evidence reveals
359 prior classifications, annotations, or assemblies are no longer accurate, e.g., the recent work
360 of Nguyen and others (78–80). Consequently, older genome entries produced under
361 outdated taxonomic frameworks, legacy methods, or initial assumptions often persist
362 uncorrected in these databases. When subsequent studies unknowingly reuse such legacy
363 data, they may propagate obsolete interpretations and effectively contaminate modern
364 analyses, reinforcing a cycle of wrongness in which results appear consistent but rest on
365 outdated information. In essence, reproducibility alone cannot guarantee true biological
366 validity if reference databases fail to keep pace with new scientific insights: one can faithfully
367 replicate past findings yet still fall out of step with current scientific truth. This reality
368 underscores that data stewardship involves more than simply collecting and providing data.
369 An ideal genomic data ecosystem would include continuous curation and versioning of
370 reference records, near real time dissemination and verification of updated annotations or
371 reclassifications, and richer, standardized metadata to enable downstream researchers to
372 reinterpret legacy datasets as knowledge evolves. Although implementing such practices is
373 challenging under current community-submission models (especially given the frequent
374 lack of comprehensive metadata), strengthening these stewardship mechanisms is
375 increasingly crucial to ensure that shared genomic resources remain as up to date, accurate,
376 and trustworthy as the science they underpin.

377 Metadata quality and computational provenance determine whether such wrongness can
378 be recognized and investigated after the fact. Missing sample-level metadata, non-
379 standardized descriptors, and incomplete method reporting do not merely reduce
380 convenience; they directly limit the ability of other investigators to distinguish true biological
381 variation from contamination, sample-quality imbalance, sample mislabeling, or analytical
382 artifacts (5, 6, 22, 44, 48, 74). Rajesh et al. (2021) found that substantial metadata are lost
383 between publications and public repositories, while Huang et al. (2025) showed that critical
384 metadata omissions remain widespread across public omics studies. At the computational
385 level, incomplete documentation of workflow requirements, software versions, parameters,
386 and execution environments can prevent meaningful reanalysis or even successful re-
387 execution. This is precisely why provenance-focused efforts such as BioCompute emerged
388 (50): not because reproducibility was solved, but because the archives and publications
389 alone often fail to capture enough information to interpret what was actually done. Lastly,
390 these issues have real economic consequences as well, by some estimates as high as \$28
391 billion in research funding is wasted annually in the U.S. alone (81).

392 Challenges for Digital Biology

393 Ultimately, the issues described above extend into the integrity of AI-enabled biology, going
394 far beyond classical reproducibility and data provenance issues. Public genomic data are
395 increasingly reused for model training, benchmarking, and reference-set construction. If
396 those data are missing material origin information or have unresolved contamination,
397 metadata inconsistencies, provenance gaps, or duplicated and mislabeled records, the
398 resulting models may appear performant while encoding hidden biases or failure modes
399 inherited from the training corpus (7). Recent standards-focused reviews have explicitly
400 noted that data-quality variability, inconsistent metadata, and reuse barriers in genomic
401 archives could affect emerging AI models under development (7, 22, 44).

402 For digital biology, data provenance and structured metadata are a matter of enabling
403 infrastructure. Recent advances in AI-enabled biology already illustrate this, with AlphaFold
404 representing the clearest positive example. In the original AlphaFold paper, it was stated that
405 the model was possible because it could train to high accuracy using supervised learning on
406 Protein Data Bank (PDB) data (82). Subsequent PDB reviews have been even more explicit:
407 rigorously validated and expertly biocurated PDB structures are considered a gold-standard
408 resource that has made AI/ML prediction of protein structures possible (83). This did not
409 happen because the PDB was merely a large, comprehensive database, but rather because
410 it has maintained a very high level of rigorous deposition standards, formal validation, expert
411 biocuration, and public validation reports since its inception (84). In short, AlphaFold was
412 enabled not only by architecture and compute, but by decades of disciplined, human-in-the-
413 loop data stewardship.

414 In contrast, genome-scale foundation models are being developed under much less
415 favorable data conditions. Evo 2 was trained on 9 trillion DNA base pairs from a “highly
416 curated genomic atlas” (OpenGenome2), whose corpus was compiled from curated, non-
417 redundant nucleotide data spanning bacteria, archaea, eukaryotes, and bacteriophages
418 (85). Interestingly, OpenGenome2 was not based on NCBI’s RefSeq, but instead was based
419 on GTDB (86), IMG/VR (87), and IMG/PR (88), with additional layers of automated curation
420 applied in all cases to further quality-filter the resulting data used for building
421 OpenGenome2 and training Evo 2. Likewise, the recently published Nucleotide Transformer
422 model also did not simply ingest arbitrary public genomes; its pretraining was selected from
423 RefSeq on the basis of assembly quality and species diversity, yet significant manual
424 curation of records was still needed for model development (89). Similarly, CellFM
425 development was directly hampered by technical noise and batch effects across single-cell
426 sequencing datasets, which required extensive standardized data cleansing of public
427 datasets into unified formats before training (90). Another single-cell AI model being

428 developed, SCimilarity, had the same challenges: pan-body analyses were hampered by
429 dataset curation and harmonization challenges stemming from gaps in metadata and a lack
430 of standardized pre-processing methodologies (91). A recent review of large single-cell
431 genomics atlases reinforces these points (92). Thus, even in the emerging field of genomics
432 foundation models, developers are already compensating for uneven public data quality and
433 poorly documented metadata by imposing additional filters, human curation decisions, and
434 label controls before training or evaluation.

435 Benchmarking and evaluation introduce an additional layer of risk. The Nucleotide
436 Transformer authors explicitly note that Enformer’s performance in their benchmark might
437 be inflated because the model had originally been trained using different data splits, creating
438 potential data leakage (89). A later benchmark of DNA foundation models reached a similar
439 conclusion from another angle, showing that pretraining data composition and metadata
440 accuracy materially affect downstream performance (93). Consistent with these concerns,
441 Joeres et al. recently introduced DataSAIL, a framework aimed at helping prevent overly
442 optimistic benchmark results driven by information leakage rather than true model
443 generalization (94).

444 Establishing Reference Source Materials

445 In 2018, ATCC launched the Enhanced Authentication Initiative (EAI) to perform whole-
446 genome sequencing on 250 microbial strains that serve as critical reference materials for
447 clinical microbiology and were known to have significantly divergent genome references in
448 public databases. At a high level, the goal of the EAI was to establish ground truth for these
449 microbes’ genomes by sequencing materials directly from ATCC’s reference collection. This
450 program was later expanded in 2019 with the launch of the ATCC Genome Portal (AGP,
451 <https://genomes.atcc.org>), which has the implicit goal of creating high-quality genomic
452 reference data for all materials held within ATCC’s living collection (95). Today, the AGP is
453 composed entirely of genomic data produced in-house by ATCC for 7,000 microbes and
454 nearly 1,000 human and animal cell lines (as of June, 2026). All of the data were generated
455 directly from source materials in ATCC’s collection, using both Oxford Nanopore
456 Technologies and Illumina sequencing technologies, and subsequently layered with expertly
457 curated provenance and sample source data, genome annotations, resistome data,
458 methylation data, transcriptomics data, and genomic variant data for thousands of ATCC
459 microbes, human and animal cell lines, and viruses.

460 ATCC’s initiative was not the first to establish clear provenance between materials and the
461 genomic data representing them. Early examples of this can be found in the Cancer Cell Line
462 Encyclopedia (CCLE), which was initiated in 2006 as a collaboration between Novartis and

463 the Broad Institute and released in 2012 (96). CCLE included multiomics data for ~1,000 cell
464 lines commonly used across the biopharma and cancer research domains and aimed to
465 create a digital atlas for benchmarking and exploratory studies. The provenance of the
466 materials used for CCLE, however, has come into question multiple times since the initial
467 landmark publication. Significant genetic and pharmacogenomic discrepancies between its
468 database and other major repositories, such as the Sanger Institute's, have been
469 documented by multiple independent studies (97–99). An early study, which was later
470 openly debated, identified issues with passage history and secondary distribution as
471 potential sources of differences between CCLE and the Cancer Genome Project (CGP),
472 where a lack of direct traceability to certified lots (like those from ATCC) may have
473 contributed to mislabeled lines or irreproducible drug-response data. A later study identified
474 106 "identical" cell lines shared between these institutes that showed only a 57% overlap in
475 mutations, suggesting that many lines have evolved into genetically distinct strains rather
476 than being identical reagents and, more importantly, that these materials had not been
477 directly sourced from a common biorepository or culture collection (100). The general issues
478 around cell line authenticity and the importance of provenance specifically were later
479 reviewed in 2018 by Hynds et al. (101). A systematic comparison of ATCC's own 'omics data
480 for the ~1,000 cell lines currently included in the AGP against those from CCLE and CGP is
481 underway.

482 In microbiology, similar efforts have been undertaken. For example, a consortium was led by
483 the U.S. FDA to create the FDA-ARGOS BioProject where 487 human pathogen "reference
484 strains" were sequenced using "regulatory-grade" quality criteria (102). This cohort of data
485 was later expanded to include genome assemblies for 1,428 microbes. The FDA-ARGOS
486 database introduced additional hurdles to its utility, however, by intentionally renaming
487 known strains, some available in culture collections, with new "FDAARGOS_####" strain
488 designations. It is also notable that at least 83 (~5.8%) of the assemblies in the FDA-ARGOS
489 BioProject (PRJNA231221) have subsequently been marked as "atypical" by NCBI's
490 automated systems either for potential source material ambiguity, taxonomic
491 misclassification, or contamination (e.g., ~74 have greater than 5% contamination by
492 CheckM using family-specific markers) and as a result, are suppressed genomes. Lastly,
493 since many of the isolates used for FDA-ARGOS were sourced from non-public clinical
494 microbiology laboratory collections, and the associated strain identifiers for publicly
495 available strains were renamed, replicating the results of FDA-ARGOS even for a small
496 number of isolates remains a substantial challenge. Collectively, this limits the ability of the
497 broader research community to associate these reference genomes with existing type-
498 strains or clinical reference strain identifiers and therefore limits the utility of the data.

499 In a separate effort, the National Collection of Type Cultures (NCTC) created the NCTC3000
500 collection where 2,234 whole-genome assemblies were produced using only PacBio data
501 (103). The effort primarily focused on bacterial pathogens, with an emphasis on type strains
502 and historical isolates from the Public Health England’s NCTC. In a similar vein, the Japanese
503 Collection of Microorganisms (JCM) carried out whole-genome sequencing of 351
504 authenticated prokaryote strains for which no prior reference genome was available, an
505 effort that helps expand the overall diversity of microbial genomic data for otherwise
506 neglected organisms (104). Like ATCC’s AGP initiative, the NCTC3000 collection is derived
507 from authenticated strains and culture collection numbers (NCTC IDs) link directly to stored
508 vials in the biobank for each assembly.

509 A similar effort was undertaken using a democratized consortium approach by the World
510 Federation of Culture Collections’ (WFCC) 10K genomes project (105), which currently is
511 ~20% complete (e.g., see BioProject #PRJDB9057). Importantly, while the WFCC project
512 outlines protocols and methods for participating sequencing centers, the metadata
513 captured, sourcing of materials, sample processing, and handling of the isolates was not
514 standardized and left to submitting researchers to decide. This may be one of the underlying
515 reasons why ~20% of the assemblies have >5% contamination scores (e.g., see CheckM
516 values using family level marker indices as reported in PRJDB9057). Furthermore, some of
517 the physical source materials used for each assembly were deposited into culture
518 collections by researchers after the data were made available, which creates gaps in the
519 tracking of sample handling. In fact, 109 of the assemblies in this BioProject are “atypical”
520 and not attributable to a known collection. Thus, while this initiative aims to create a linkage
521 between genomic data and physical strains, in practice the provenance of the data has
522 created a high degree of uncertainty in the accuracy of the results. This is in contrast to the
523 “sourced from the collection first” approach taken by ATCC, the JCM, and the NCTC.

524 As the AGP has grown, and as our own methods have improved as new technologies and
525 bioinformatics tools have emerged, so too has the quality and comprehensiveness of our
526 data. Furthermore, these changes have demanded re-evaluation of how datasets are linked
527 to one another, what metadata are captured, what criteria are necessary to establish
528 provenance and trust, and how these can be provided to end-users of the AGP. This is an
529 iterative exercise in the case of the AGP as community needs change and ATCC’s capabilities
530 increase. This “living database” model is one of the key differentiators between ATCC’s
531 initiative and (at scale) it is likely not feasible for massive community-driven data archives
532 like RefSeq, but it is plausible for culture collections to achieve.

533 Taken together, these efforts illustrate that trustworthy genomic reference data are enabled
534 not by sequencing scale or technological sophistication alone, but by the sequencing of
535 materials whose physical provenance, handling history, and custodial chain are well defined

536 at the outset. Initiatives such as the AGP and NCTC3000 exemplify a “collection-first” model,
537 in which genomic data are generated directly from authenticated, traceable source
538 materials. In contrast, sequence-first or community-aggregated efforts often struggle to
539 retrospectively establish provenance, even when data quality metrics appear strong. This
540 distinction has important implications for how genomic reference resources are
541 constructed, curated, benchmarked, and trusted, particularly as such datasets increasingly
542 underpin clinical, regulatory, and AI-driven biological analyses.

543 Discussion

544 Standards for genomics metadata and provenance are not the limiting factor:
545 implementation and enforcement of those standards is. Community frameworks such as
546 MlxS/MIGS (10, 11, 106), Darwin Core (e.g., GGBN) (107, 108), public health specifications
547 (e.g., PHA4GE) (109, 110), and workflow provenance standards (e.g., BioCompute) (50) all
548 make the same underlying claim: genomic sequences are only meaningfully reusable when
549 they remain connected to (i) a traceable physical sample or specimen, (ii) the key contextual
550 descriptors of how that sample was collected and processed, and (iii) the computational
551 methods used to transform raw reads into the deposited record. Yet in major public archives,
552 critical provenance fields remain optional, inconsistently populated, and weakly validated,
553 so records frequently preserve the sequence more reliably than the evidence needed to
554 interpret, replicate, reproduce, or validate it (22, 48, 74).

555 A core gap is that the provenance of sample origins, handling, and primary sample
556 processing methodologies are not mandated as a first-class, “metadata as infrastructure”
557 requirement. Instead, it is applied inconsistently through a patchwork of different labeling
558 schemas and requirements. Even when standards define “source material identifiers” or
559 voucher linkages, public repositories often accept submissions without persistent
560 connections to the originating biomaterial, leaving no reliable chain-of-custody and no
561 practical route to obtain the original material for confirmation (5, 6, 42, 43, 48, 71, 74). This
562 is not a niche concern: across multiple domains, metadata incompleteness and
563 inconsistency remain widespread, and the burden of reconstruction falls to downstream
564 end users rather than depositors.

565 A second gap is that the provenance of the computational methods used is not captured in
566 a consistently machine-readable way (46, 47, 111). Archive schemas may store platform
567 and basic run metadata, but critical details needed for replication (i.e., specific software
568 versions, parameters, reference resources, filtering/contamination screening decisions, and
569 validation logic) are often relegated to free text or (more commonly) omitted entirely. The
570 existence of separate provenance standards like BioCompute reflects this reality: they arose

571 because repositories and papers alone frequently fail to preserve enough workflow detail for
572 reliable re-execution or regulatory-grade traceability (50, 112). Notably, BioCompute
573 Objects have been identified formally by the FDA as an acceptable model for tracking the
574 provenance of submissions for regulatory decisions (113). Similarly, the FAANG and
575 ENCODE metadata models are examples of data standards requiring rich metadata for
576 sample and data provenance. FAANG explicitly framed rich sample and experimental
577 metadata as a core goal (114), and ENCODE organizes assay and computational metadata
578 as structured schema objects (115). Yet, despite these major efforts to develop accessible,
579 open interoperability standards that will work broadly with genomic data, these models have
580 not been integrated into major public data repositories and remain largely parallel standards
581 to the arguably less rigorous MIxS standards widely in use.

582 Finally, the public archive ingestion model prioritizes scale over verification. For example,
583 GenBank is built primarily from direct submissions by researchers and sequencing centers,
584 underscoring that deposition is not intrinsically gated by peer review or independent
585 validation. Data depositors can update records after they are released with links to related
586 peer-reviewed publications, but in practice this is not a guarantee. It's interesting to note the
587 historical contrast of this approach to Goad's original intent for the Los Alamos DNA Data
588 Bank, wherein all records would be labeled as "provisional" unless they were independently
589 validated (1). Thus, public sequence repositories function as enormous data lakes with
590 uneven provenance rather than curated reference resources: they maximize openness and
591 volume, but provide limited guarantees about sample origin, authenticity, handling history,
592 or computational traceability. This structural gap creates an ongoing challenge for method
593 validation studies, complicates comparative genomics, imposes obstacles for genomics-
594 driven public health responsiveness, and hampers the development and training of high-
595 accuracy AIxBio models for digital biology applications.

596 When Walter Goad proposed the first centralized DNA sequence repository in 1979, he
597 stressed the importance of collecting "complete information on DNA origin," including the
598 source organism and even original lab records for verification. Goad's vision included
599 archiving gel electrophoresis autoradiograms and detailed sample information on microfilm
600 alongside sequence data to ensure that future users could evaluate a sequence's
601 authenticity and quality (1). In many ways, current calls for data provenance echo those
602 early recommendations. The fact that the community is still grappling with missing metadata
603 suggests that provenance and authenticity have been chronically undervalued for decades.

604 Public genomics repositories have been indispensable for accelerating discovery, but their
605 current "archive-first" operating model leaves a growing trust gap: sequences are often
606 preserved more reliably than the evidence needed to interpret, reproduce, or validate them.
607 As datasets scale and downstream reuse expands, especially for AIxBio applications,

608 missing or inconsistent provenance (sample origins, handling history, and chain-of-custody)
609 and incomplete computational provenance (software, parameters, reference resources,
610 and QC decisions) increasingly translate into irreproducible findings, silent error
611 propagation, and exploitable opportunities for fabrication or misuse. As a result, the life
612 sciences community is now investing significant effort to retrofit these databases with better
613 metadata at considerable costs, an endeavor that will be crucial for the next era of data-
614 driven biology.

615 In addition, while prevention is essential, the scale of historical metadata gaps in public
616 repositories cannot be ignored either. Strategic, targeted retrospective curation prioritized
617 around high-value reference records (e.g. clinical and regulatory use cases) and widely
618 reused benchmarking datasets will be necessary. Doing so will substantially aid in mitigating
619 existing risks, even if comprehensive remediation is infeasible. Efforts to curate legacy data
620 should therefore be treated as an infrastructure investment and aligned with clear
621 incentives, automated where possible, and guided by realistic expectations about what can
622 and cannot be recovered after the fact.

623 In conclusion, the genomics and digital biology community does not need to reinvent
624 standards; the existing standards the genomics community has already created must be
625 enforced in ways that reduce friction for submitters while materially improving
626 interoperability, traceability, and reuse. Critically, physical reference samples and the
627 metadata that describe their origin, handling, and transformation should be treated as
628 shared scientific infrastructure that is proactively preserved, persistently identified, and
629 curated with the same long-term intent as reference genomes or computational resources.
630 Culture collections and biorepositories can uniquely bridge the physical-to-digital divide by
631 anchoring verifiable “digital twins” to authenticated source materials (41, 43, 95), while data
632 repositories and journals can drive adoption through raising the minimum deposition
633 requirements for metadata, better submission tooling, and visible incentives for strong
634 provenance. The genomics community has long championed open data; the next step is to
635 champion *trustworthy* data sharing so that the future of digital biology and AI-enabled
636 biology is built on traceable, defensible, and reusable genomic records, rather than on an
637 assumption of trust.

638 References

- 639 1. W. B. Goad, “Proposal to establish a national center for collection, and computer
640 storage and analysis of nucleic acid sequences.” (Proposal, University of California.
641 Los Alamos Scientific Laboratory, 1979); <https://hdl.handle.net/10822/556965>.
- 642 2. E. Jordan, C. Carrico, DNA Database. *Science* **218**, 108–108 (1982).

- 643 3. National Center for Biotechnology Information, GenBank and WGS Statistics,
644 *GenBank and WGS Statistics* (2026).
645 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/statistics/>).
- 646 4. J. C. Buckner, R. C. Sanders, B. C. Faircloth, P. Chakrabarty, The critical importance of
647 vouchers in genomics. *eLife* **10**, e68264 (2021).
- 648 5. J. B. Pettengill, J. Beal, M. Balkey, M. Allard, H. Rand, R. Timme, Interpretative Labor
649 and the Bane of Nonstandardized Metadata in Public Health Surveillance and Food
650 Safety. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* **73**, 1537–1539 (2021).
- 651 6. A. Rajesh, Y. Chang, M. S. Abedalthagafi, A. Wong-Beringer, M. I. Love, S. Mangul,
652 Improving the completeness of public metadata accompanying omics studies.
653 *Genome Biol* **22**, 106, s13059-021-02332-z (2021).
- 654 7. I. Keenum, S. A. Jackson, E. Eloë-Fadrosh, L. M. Schriml, A standards perspective on
655 genomic data reusability and reproducibility. *Front. Bioinform.* **5**, 1572937 (2025).
- 656 8. G. Cochrane, I. Karsch-Mizrachi, T. Takagi, I. N. Sequence Database Collaboration,
657 The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration. *Nucleic Acids Res*
658 **44**, D48–D50 (2016).
- 659 9. A. Astashyn, E. S. Tvedte, D. Sweeney, V. Sapojnikov, N. Bouk, V. Joukov, E. Mozes, P.
660 K. Strobe, P. M. Sylla, L. Wagner, S. L. Bidwell, L. C. Brown, K. Clark, E. W. Davis, B.
661 Smith-White, W. Hlavina, K. D. Pruitt, V. A. Schneider, T. D. Murphy, Rapid and
662 sensitive detection of genome contamination at scale with FCS-GX. *Genome Biol* **25**,
663 60 (2024).
- 664 10. D. Field, G. Garrity, T. Gray, N. Morrison, J. Selengut, P. Sterk, T. Tatusova, N.
665 Thomson, M. J. Allen, S. V. Angiuoli, M. Ashburner, N. Axelrod, S. Baldauf, S. Ballard, J.
666 Boore, G. Cochrane, J. Cole, P. Dawyndt, P. De Vos, C. dePamphilis, R. Edwards, N.
667 Faruque, R. Feldman, J. Gilbert, P. Gilna, F. O. Glöckner, P. Goldstein, R. Guralnick, D.
668 Haft, D. Hancock, H. Hermjakob, C. Hertz-Fowler, P. Hugenholtz, I. Joint, L. Kagan, M.
669 Kane, J. Kennedy, G. Kowalchuk, R. Kottmann, E. Kolker, S. Kravitz, N. Kyrpides, J.
670 Leebens-Mack, S. E. Lewis, K. Li, A. L. Lister, P. Lord, N. Maltsev, V. Markowitz, J.
671 Martiny, B. Methe, I. Mizrachi, R. Moxon, K. Nelson, J. Parkhill, L. Proctor, O. White, S.-
672 A. Sansone, A. Spiers, R. Stevens, P. Swift, C. Taylor, Y. Tateno, A. Tett, S. Turner, D.
673 Ussery, B. Vaughan, N. Ward, T. Whetzel, I. San Gil, G. Wilson, A. Wipat, The
674 minimum information about a genome sequence (MIGS) specification. *Nature*
675 *Biotechnology* **26**, 541–547 (2008).
- 676 11. P. Yilmaz, R. Kottmann, D. Field, R. Knight, J. R. Cole, L. Amaral-Zettler, J. A. Gilbert, I.
677 Karsch-Mizrachi, A. Johnston, G. Cochrane, R. Vaughan, C. Hunter, J. Park, N.
678 Morrison, P. Rocca-Serra, P. Sterk, M. Arumugam, M. Bailey, L. Baumgartner, B. W.
679 Birren, M. J. Blaser, V. Bonazzi, T. Booth, P. Bork, F. D. Bushman, P. L. Buttigieg, P. S. G.

- 680 Chain, E. Charlson, E. K. Costello, H. Huot-Creasy, P. Dawyndt, T. DeSantis, N. Fierer,
681 J. A. Fuhrman, R. E. Gallery, D. Gevers, R. A. Gibbs, I. S. Gil, A. Gonzalez, J. I. Gordon,
682 R. Guralnick, W. Hankeln, S. Highlander, P. Hugenholtz, J. Jansson, A. L. Kau, S. T.
683 Kelley, J. Kennedy, D. Knights, O. Koren, J. Kuczynski, N. Kyrpides, R. Larsen, C. L.
684 Lauber, T. Legg, R. E. Ley, C. A. Lozupone, W. Ludwig, D. Lyons, E. Maguire, B. A.
685 Methé, F. Meyer, B. Muegge, S. Nakielnny, K. E. Nelson, D. Nemergut, J. D. Neufeld, L.
686 K. Newbold, A. E. Oliver, N. R. Pace, G. Palanisamy, J. Peplies, J. Petrosino, L. Proctor,
687 E. Pruesse, C. Quast, J. Raes, S. Ratnasingham, J. Ravel, D. A. Relman, S. Assunta-
688 Sansone, P. D. Schloss, L. Schriml, R. Sinha, M. I. Smith, E. Sodergren, A. Spor, J.
689 Stombaugh, J. M. Tiedje, D. V. Ward, G. M. Weinstock, D. Wendel, O. White, A.
690 Whiteley, A. Wilke, J. R. Wortman, T. Yatsunenko, F. O. Glöckner, Minimum
691 information about a marker gene sequence (MIMARKS) and minimum information
692 about any (x) sequence (MlxS) specifications. *Nat Biotechnol* **29**, 415–420 (2011).
- 693 12. Genomic Standards Consortium, MIXS Checklists (2026).
694 <https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/#checklists>.
- 695 13. G. Sangster, J. A. Luksenburg, Scientific data laundering: Chimeric mitogenomes of a
696 sparrowhawk and a nightjar covered-up by forged phylogenies. *Biochemical*
697 *Systematics and Ecology* **96**, 104263 (2021).
- 698 14. D. A. Yarmosh, J. G. Lopera, N. P. Puthuveetil, P. F. Combs, A. L. Reese, C. Tabron, A.
699 E. Pierola, J. Duncan, S. R. Greenfield, R. Marlow, S. King, M. A. Riojas, J. Bagnoli, B.
700 Benton, J. L. Jacobs, Comparative Analysis and Data Provenance for 1,113 Bacterial
701 Genome Assemblies. *bioRxiv*, doi: 10.1101/2021.12.14.472616 (2021).
- 702 15. E. W. Sayers, M. Cavanaugh, K. Clark, K. D. Pruitt, S. T. Sherry, L. Yankie, I. Karsch-
703 Mizrahi, GenBank 2024 Update. *Nucleic Acids Res* **52**, D134–D137 (2024).
- 704 16. A. Carné, D. R. Vieites, M. P. Van Den Burg, In Vouchers We (Hope to) Trust: Unveiling
705 Hidden Errors in GENBANK 's Tetrapod Taxonomic Foundations. *Molecular Ecology* **34**,
706 e17812 (2025).
- 707 17. M. I. Bidartondo, Preserving Accuracy in GenBank. *Science* **319**, 1616–1616 (2008).
- 708 18. The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, From January 2025
709 TPA-Exp and TPA-Inf submission types will no longer be accepted as new
710 submissions (03-09-2024) (2024). <https://www.insdc.org/news/from-january-2025-tpa-exp-and-tpa-inf-submission-types-will-no-longer-be-accepted-as-new-submissions-03-09-2024/>.
- 713 19. O. K. Tørresen, B. Star, P. Mier, M. A. Andrade-Navarro, A. Bateman, P. Jarnot, A.
714 Gruca, M. Grynberg, A. V. Kajava, V. J. Promponas, M. Anisimova, K. S. Jakobsen, D.
715 Linke, Tandem repeats lead to sequence assembly errors and impose multi-level

- 716 challenges for genome and protein databases. *Nucleic Acids Research* **47**, 10994–
717 11006 (2019).
- 718 20. R. H. Toczydlowski, L. Liggins, M. R. Gaither, T. J. Anderson, R. L. Barton, J. T. Berg, S.
719 G. Beskid, B. Davis, A. Delgado, E. Farrell, M. Ghoojarei, N. Himmelsbach, A. E.
720 Holmes, S. R. Queeno, T. Trinh, C. A. Weyand, G. S. Bradburd, C. Riginos, R. J. Toonen,
721 E. D. Crandall, Poor data stewardship will hinder global genetic diversity surveillance.
722 *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **118**, e2107934118 (2021).
- 723 21. E. D. Crandall, R. H. Toczydlowski, L. Liggins, A. E. Holmes, M. Ghoojarei, M. R.
724 Gaither, B. E. Wham, A. L. Pritt, C. Noble, T. J. Anderson, R. L. Barton, J. T. Berg, S. G.
725 Beskid, A. Delgado, E. Farrell, N. Himmelsbach, S. R. Queeno, T. Trinh, C. Weyand, A.
726 Bentley, J. Deck, C. Riginos, G. S. Bradburd, R. J. Toonen, Importance of timely
727 metadata curation to the global surveillance of genetic diversity. *Conservation*
728 *Biology* **37**, e14061 (2023).
- 729 22. Y.-N. Huang, P. V. Jaiswal, A. Rajes, A. Yadav, D. Yu, F. Liu, G. Scheg, E. Shih, G.
730 Boldirev, I. Nakashidze, A. Sarkar, J. H. Mehta, K. Wang, K. K. Patel, M. A. B. Mirza, K.
731 C. Hapani, Q. Peng, R. Ayyala, R. Guo, S. Kapur, T. Ramesh, D. Ciorbă, V. Munteanu, V.
732 Bostan, M. Dimian, M. S. Abedalthagafi, S. Mangul, The systematic assessment of
733 completeness of public metadata accompanying omics studies in the Gene
734 Expression Omnibus data repository. *Genome Biol* **26**, 274 (2025).
- 735 23. H. Bagheri, A. J. Severin, H. Rajan, Detecting and correcting misclassified sequences
736 in the large-scale public databases. *Bioinformatics* **36**, 4699–4705 (2020).
- 737 24. A. Gihawi, Y. Ge, J. Lu, D. Puiu, A. Xu, C. S. Cooper, D. S. Brewer, M. Pertea, S. L.
738 Salzberg, Major data analysis errors invalidate cancer microbiome findings. *mBio* **14**,
739 e01607-23 (2023).
- 740 25. V. Lupo, M. Van Vlierberghe, H. Vanderschuren, F. Kerff, D. Baurain, L. Cornet,
741 Contamination in Reference Sequence Databases: Time for Divide-and-Rule Tactics.
742 *Front. Microbiol.* **12**, 755101 (2021).
- 743 26. M. Steinegger, S. L. Salzberg, Terminating contamination: large-scale search
744 identifies more than 2,000,000 contaminated entries in GenBank. *Genome Biol* **21**,
745 115 (2020).
- 746 27. J. A. Byrne, N. Grima, A. Capes-Davis, C. Labbé, The Possibility of Systematic
747 Research Fraud Targeting Under-Studied Human Genes: Causes, Consequences,
748 and Potential Solutions. *Biomark Insights* **14**, 117727191982916 (2019).
- 749 28. R. A. K. Richardson, S. S. Hong, J. A. Byrne, T. Stoeger, L. A. N. Amaral, The entities
750 enabling scientific fraud at scale are large, resilient, and growing rapidly. *Proc. Natl.*
751 *Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **122**, e2420092122 (2025).

- 752 29. Y.-M. Kim, J.-B. Poline, G. Dumas, Experimenting with reproducibility: a case study of
753 robustness in bioinformatics. *GigaScience* **7** (2018).
- 754 30. J. Leipzig, D. Nüst, C. T. Hoyt, S. Soiland-Reyes, K. Ram, J. Greenberg, The role of
755 metadata in reproducible computational research. *arXiv:2006.08589 [cs]* (2021).
- 756 31. F. Li, J. Hu, K. Xie, T.-C. He, Authentication of experimental materials: A remedy for
757 the reproducibility crisis? *Genes Dis* **2**, 283 (2015).
- 758 32. N. S. Locatelli, P. B. McIntyre, N. O. Therkildsen, D. S. Baetscher, GenBank’s reliability
759 is uncertain for biodiversity researchers seeking species-level assignment for eDNA.
760 *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **117**, 32211–32212 (2020).
- 761 33. B. Tang, X. Hu, M. Yue, Contaminated bacterial genome data in the public domains:
762 Evidence and solution. *Journal of Infection* **89**, 106369 (2024).
- 763 34. S. D. Chorlton, Ten common issues with reference sequence databases and how to
764 mitigate them. *Front. Bioinform.* **4**, 1278228 (2024).
- 765 35. C.-T. Berezin, S. Peccoud, D. M. Kar, J. Peccoud, Cryptographic approaches to
766 authenticating synthetic DNA sequences. *Trends in Biotechnology* **42**, 1002–1016
767 (2024).
- 768 36. C. J. Carlson, M. Granados, A. Phelan, N. Ramakrishnan, T. Poisot, The LISTEN
769 principles for genetic sequence data governance and database engineering. *Nat*
770 *Genet* **57**, 2099–2105 (2025).
- 771 37. D. Bloomfield, J. R. M. Black, O. Crook, N. Brandes, M. S. Hanke, T. V. Inglesby, A.
772 Cicero, R. Pollack, T. Hernandez-Boussard, M. J. Imperiale, R. B. Altman, J. Pannu,
773 Biological data governance in an age of AI. *Science* **391**, 558–561 (2026).
- 774 38. D. A. Yarmosh, J. G. Lopera, N. P. Puthuveetil, P. F. Combs, A. L. Reese, C. Tabron, A.
775 E. Pierola, J. Duncan, S. R. Greenfield, R. Marlow, S. King, M. A. Riojas, J. Bagnoli, B.
776 Benton, J. L. Jacobs, Comparative Analysis and Data Provenance for 1,113 Bacterial
777 Genome Assemblies. *mSphere*, e00077-22 (2022).
- 778 39. R. R. Cheng, R. L. Bradford, A foundation for tomorrow’s discoveries in cell biology.
779 *Nat Cell Biol*, doi: 10.1038/s41556-025-01824-5 (2025).
- 780 40. Committee on Biological Collections: Their Past, Present, and Future Contributions
781 and Options for Sustaining Them, Board on Life Sciences, Division on Earth and Life
782 Studies, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, *Biological*
783 *Collections: Ensuring Critical Research and Education for the 21st Century* (National
784 Academies Press, Washington, D.C., 2020;
785 <https://www.nationalacademies.org/publications/25592>).

- 786 41. C. L. Harmon, L. Castlebury, K. Boundy-Mills, K. Broders, A. M. Hyten, J. L. Jacobs, V.
787 K. Knight-Cannoni, D. Mollov, M. A. Riojas, P. Sharma, Standards of Diagnostic
788 Validation: Recommendations for reference collections. *PhytoFrontiers*TM, PHYTOFR-
789 05-22-0050-FI (2022).
- 790 42. F. Pleijel, U. Jondelius, E. Norlinder, A. Nygren, B. Oxelman, C. Schander, P. Sundberg,
791 M. Thollesson, Phylogenies without roots? A plea for the use of vouchers in
792 molecular phylogenetic studies. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* **48**, 369–371
793 (2008).
- 794 43. C. W. Thompson, K. L. Phelps, M. W. Allard, J. A. Cook, J. L. Dunnum, A. W. Ferguson,
795 M. Gelang, F. A. A. Khan, D. L. Paul, D. M. Reeder, N. B. Simmons, M. P. M. Vanhove, P.
796 W. Webala, M. Weksler, C. W. Kilpatrick, Preserve a Voucher Specimen! The Critical
797 Need for Integrating Natural History Collections in Infectious Disease Studies. *mBio*
798 **12**, e02698-20 (2021).
- 799 44. L. Kim, A. Lavrinienko, Z. Sebechlebska, S. Stoltenberg, N. A. Bokulich, Tier-based
800 standards for FAIR sequence data and metadata sharing in microbiome research.
801 *Nucleic Acids Res* **53**, gkaf777 (2025).
- 802 45. SRA Metadata and Submission Overview.
803 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/docs/submitmeta/>.
- 804 46. J. Alnasir, H. P. Shanahan, Investigation into the annotation of protocol sequencing
805 steps in the sequence read archive. *Gigascience* **4**, s13742-015-0064–7 (2015).
- 806 47. M. N. Bernstein, A. Doan, C. N. Dewey, MetaSRA: normalized human sample-specific
807 metadata for the Sequence Read Archive. *Bioinformatics* **33**, 2914–2923 (2017).
- 808 48. R. S. Gonçalves, M. A. Musen, The variable quality of metadata about biological
809 samples used in biomedical experiments. *Sci Data* **6**, 190021 (2019).
- 810 49. S. Kanwal, F. Z. Khan, A. Lonie, R. O. Sinnott, Investigating reproducibility and
811 tracking provenance – A genomic workflow case study. *BMC Bioinformatics* **18**, 337
812 (2017).
- 813 50. J. A. Patel, D. A. Dean, C. H. King, N. Xiao, S. Koc, E. Minina, A. Golikov, P. Brooks, R.
814 Kahsay, R. Navelkar, M. Ray, D. Roberson, C. Armstrong, R. Mazumder, J. Keeney,
815 Bioinformatics tools developed to support BioCompute Objects. *Database (Oxford)*
816 **2021**, baab008 (2021).
- 817 51. K. Gierend, F. Krüger, S. Genehr, F. Hartmann, F. Siegel, D. Waltemath, T. Ganslandt,
818 A. A. Zeleke, Provenance Information for Biomedical Data and Workflows: Scoping
819 Review. *J Med Internet Res* **26**, e51297 (2024).

- 820 52. D. Fanelli, How Many Scientists Fabricate and Falsify Research? A Systematic Review
821 and Meta-Analysis of Survey Data. *PLoS ONE* **4**, e5738 (2009).
- 822 53. G. Gopalakrishna, G. Ter Riet, G. Vink, I. Stoop, J. M. Wicherts, L. M. Bouter,
823 Prevalence of questionable research practices, research misconduct and their
824 potential explanatory factors: A survey among academic researchers in The
825 Netherlands. *PLoS ONE* **17**, e0263023 (2022).
- 826 54. B. A. Sabel, E. Knaack, G. Gigerenzer, M.-I. Bilc, Fake publications in biomedical
827 science: red-flagging method indicates mass production. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's*
828 *Arch Pharmacol* **399**, 2943–2955 (2026).
- 829 55. B. Scancar, J. A. Byrne, D. Causeur, A. G. Barnett, Machine learning based screening
830 of potential paper mill publications in cancer research: methodological and cross
831 sectional study. *BMJ* **392**, e087581 (2026).
- 832 56. D. C. Richter, F. Ott, A. F. Auch, R. Schmid, D. H. Huson, MetaSim—A Sequencing
833 Simulator for Genomics and Metagenomics. *PLoS ONE* **3**, e3373 (2008).
- 834 57. Y. Ono, K. Asai, M. Hamada, PBSIM2: a simulator for long-read sequencers with a
835 novel generative model of quality scores. *Bioinformatics* **37**, 589–595 (2021).
- 836 58. Y. Li, S. Wang, C. Bi, Z. Qiu, M. Li, X. Gao, DeepSimulator1.5: a more powerful,
837 quicker and lighter simulator for Nanopore sequencing. *Bioinformatics* **36**, 2578–
838 2580 (2020).
- 839 59. H. Gourelé, O. Karlsson-Lindsjö, J. Hayer, E. Bongcam-Rudloff, Simulating Illumina
840 metagenomic data with InSilicoSeq. *Bioinformatics* **35**, 521–522 (2019).
- 841 60. A. Rambaut, N. C. Grass, Seq-Gen: an application for the Monte Carlo simulation of
842 DNA sequence evolution along phylogenetic trees. *Bioinformatics* **13**, 235–238
843 (1997).
- 844 61. G. Myers, A dataset generator for whole genome shotgun sequencing. *Proc Int Conf*
845 *Intell Syst Mol Biol*, 202–210 (1999).
- 846 62. E. Marshall, Fraud Strikes Top Genome Lab: Francis Collins, head of NIH's Human
847 Genome Project, has informed colleagues that a junior researcher in his lab faked
848 data in five papers Collins co-authored. *Science* **274**, 908–910 (1996).
- 849 63. G. Sangster, J. A. Luksenburg, Sharp Increase of Problematic Mitogenomes of Birds:
850 Causes, Consequences, and Remedies. *Genome Biology and Evolution* **13**, evab210
851 (2021).
- 852 64. M. P. Van Den Burg, D. R. Vieites, Bird genetic databases need improved curation and
853 error reporting to NCBI. *Ibis* **165**, 472–481 (2023).

- 854 65. A. Potti, H. K. Dressman, A. Bild, R. F. Riedel, G. Chan, R. Sayer, J. Cragun, H. Cottrill,
855 M. J. Kelley, R. Petersen, D. Harpole, J. Marks, A. Berchuck, G. S. Ginsburg, P. Febbo, J.
856 Lancaster, J. R. Nevins, Retraction Note: Genomic signatures to guide the use of
857 chemotherapeutics. *Nat Med* **17**, 135–135 (2011).
- 858 66. K. A. Baggerly, K. R. Coombes, Deriving chemosensitivity from cell lines: forensic
859 bioinformatics and reproducible research in high-throughput biology. *The Annals of*
860 *Applied Statistics*, 1309–1334 (2009).
- 861 67. NOT-OD-14-098: Findings of Research Misconduct, *Findings of Research Misconduct*
862 (2014). <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-14-098.html>.
- 863 68. Retraction. *Endocrinology* **150**, 2976–2976 (2009).
- 864 69. M. S. Bradshaw, S. H. Payne, Detecting fabrication in large-scale molecular omics
865 data. *PLoS ONE* **16**, e0260395 (2021).
- 866 70. M. R. Bouadjeneq, K. Verspoor, J. Zobel, Automated detection of records in biological
867 sequence databases that are inconsistent with the literature. *Journal of Biomedical*
868 *Informatics* **71**, 229–240 (2017).
- 869 71. M. Sprang, J. Möllmann, M. A. Andrade-Navarro, J.-F. Fontaine, Overlooked poor-
870 quality patient samples in sequencing data impair reproducibility of published
871 clinically relevant datasets. *Genome Biol* **25**, 222 (2024).
- 872 72. Committee on Reproducibility and Replicability in Science, Board on Behavioral,
873 Cognitive, and Sensory Sciences, Committee on National Statistics, Division of
874 Behavioral and Social Sciences and Education, Nuclear and Radiation Studies
875 Board, Division on Earth and Life Studies, Board on Mathematical Sciences and
876 Analytics, Committee on Applied and Theoretical Statistics, Division on Engineering
877 and Physical Sciences, Board on Research Data and Information, Committee on
878 Science, Engineering, Medicine, and Public Policy, Policy and Global Affairs, National
879 Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, *Reproducibility and Replicability*
880 *in Science* (National Academies Press, Washington, D.C., 2019;
881 <https://www.nationalacademies.org/publications/25303>).
- 882 73. P. I. Baykal, P. P. Łabaj, F. Markowetz, L. M. Schriml, D. J. Stekhoven, S. Mangul, N.
883 Beerwinkler, Genomic reproducibility in the bioinformatics era. *Genome Biol* **25**,
884 213 (2024).
- 885 74. R. S. Gonçalves, M. J. O’Connor, M. Martínez-Romero, J. Graybeal, M. A. Musen,
886 Metadata in the BioSample Online Repository are Impaired by Numerous Anomalies.
887 arXiv arXiv:1708.01286 [Preprint] (2017). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1708.01286>.
- 888 75. A. Bernasconi, Data quality-aware genomic data integration. *Computer Methods and*
889 *Programs in Biomedicine Update* **1**, 100009 (2021).

- 890 76. J. T. Leek, R. D. Peng, Reproducible research can still be wrong: Adopting a prevention
891 approach. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **112**, 1645–1646 (2015).
- 892 77. B. Goudey, N. Geard, K. Verspoor, J. Zobel, Propagation, detection and correction of
893 errors using the sequence database network. *Briefings in Bioinformatics* **23**, bbac416
894 (2022).
- 895 78. S. V. Nguyen, V. H. Escobar, S. S. Ali, N. P. Puthuveetil, J. R. Petrone, J. L. Kirkland, K.
896 Gaffney, C. L. Tabron, N. Wax, J. Duncan, S. King, R. Marlow, A. L. Reese, D. A.
897 Yarmosh, H. H. McConnell, A. S. Fernandes, J. Bagnoli, B. Benton, J. L. Jacobs,
898 Reclassification of atypical *Moraxella catarrhalis* ATCC 23246 as *Moraxella veridica*
899 sp. nov. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* **75** (2025).
- 900 79. N. Bouras, G. Dif, S. Belghit, S. V. Nguyen, J. L. Jacobs, O. Toumatia, S. S. Ebada, I.
901 Nouioui, Genome-based reclassification of the genus *Thermoanaerobacter*:
902 taxonomic emendations and new combinations. *Anaerobe* **97**, 103027 (2026).
- 903 80. S. V. Nguyen, D. Edwards, E. L. Vaughn, V. Escobar, S. Ali, J. H. Doss, J. T. Steyer, S.
904 Scott, W. Bchara, N. Bruns, E. Zelaya, A. Tran, D. Payne, J. R. Hauser, Expanding the
905 *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* complex: phylogenomic insights, proposal of
906 *Stenotrophomonas forensis* sp. nov. and reclassification of two *Pseudomonas*
907 species. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* **74** (2024).
- 908 81. L. P. Freedman, I. M. Cockburn, T. S. Simcoe, The Economics of Reproducibility in
909 Preclinical Research. *PLoS Biol* **13**, e1002165 (2015).
- 910 82. J. Jumper, R. Evans, A. Pritzel, T. Green, M. Figurnov, O. Ronneberger, K.
911 Tunyasuvunakool, R. Bates, A. Žídek, A. Potapenko, A. Bridgland, C. Meyer, S. A. A.
912 Kohl, A. J. Ballard, A. Cowie, B. Romera-Paredes, S. Nikolov, R. Jain, J. Adler, T. Back,
913 S. Petersen, D. Reiman, E. Clancy, M. Zielinski, M. Steinegger, M. Pacholska, T.
914 Berghammer, S. Bodenstein, D. Silver, O. Vinyals, A. W. Senior, K. Kavukcuoglu, P.
915 Kohli, D. Hassabis, Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold.
916 *Nature* **596**, 583–589 (2021).
- 917 83. S. K. Burley, C. Bhikadiya, C. Bi, S. Bittrich, H. Chao, L. Chen, P. A. Craig, G. V.
918 Crichlow, K. Dalenberg, J. M. Duarte, S. Dutta, M. Fayazi, Z. Feng, J. W. Flatt, S. J.
919 Ganesan, S. Ghosh, D. S. Goodsell, R. K. Green, V. Guranovic, J. Henry, B. P. Hudson,
920 I. Khokhriakov, C. L. Lawson, Y. Liang, R. Lowe, E. Peisach, I. Persikova, D. W. Piehl, Y.
921 Rose, A. Sali, J. Segura, M. Sekharan, C. Shao, B. Vallat, M. Voigt, B. Webb, J. D.
922 Westbrook, S. Whetstone, J. Y. Young, A. Zalevsky, C. Zardecki, RCSB Protein Data
923 bank: Tools for visualizing and understanding biological macromolecules in 3D.
924 *Protein Sci* **31**, e4482 (2022).
- 925 84. J. Y. Young, J. D. Westbrook, Z. Feng, E. Peisach, I. Persikova, R. Sala, S. Sen, J. M.
926 Berrisford, G. J. Swaminathan, T. J. Oldfield, A. Gutmanas, R. Igarashi, D. R.

- 927 Armstrong, K. Baskaran, L. Chen, M. Chen, A. R. Clark, L. Di Costanzo, D.
928 Dimitropoulos, G. Gao, S. Ghosh, S. Gore, V. Guranovic, P. M. S. Hendrickx, B. P.
929 Hudson, Y. Ikegawa, Y. Kengaku, C. L. Lawson, Y. Liang, L. Mak, A. Mukhopadhyay, B.
930 Narayanan, K. Nishiyama, A. Patwardhan, G. Sahni, E. Sanz-García, J. Sato, M. R.
931 Sekharan, C. Shao, O. S. Smart, L. Tan, G. Van Ginkel, H. Yang, M. A. Zhuravleva, J. L.
932 Markley, H. Nakamura, G. Kurisu, G. J. Kleywegt, S. Velankar, H. M. Berman, S. K.
933 Burley, Worldwide Protein Data Bank biocuration supporting open access to high-
934 quality 3D structural biology data. *Database* **2018** (2018).
- 935 85. G. Brix, M. G. Durrant, J. Ku, M. Naghipourfar, M. Poli, G. Sun, G. Brockman, D.
936 Chang, A. Fanton, G. A. Gonzalez, S. H. King, D. B. Li, A. T. Merchant, E. Nguyen, C.
937 Ricci-Tam, D. W. Romero, J. C. Schmok, A. Taghibakhshi, A. Vorontsov, B. Yang, M.
938 Deng, L. Gorton, N. Nguyen, N. K. Wang, M. T. Pearce, E. Simon, E. Adams, Z. J.
939 Amador, E. A. Ashley, S. A. Baccus, H. Dai, S. Dillmann, S. Ermon, D. Guo, M. H.
940 Herschl, R. Ilango, K. Janik, A. X. Lu, R. Mehta, M. R. K. Mofrad, M. Y. Ng, J. Pannu, C.
941 Ré, J. St. John, J. Sullivan, J. Tey, B. Viggiano, K. Zhu, G. Zynda, D. Balsam, P. Collison,
942 A. B. Costa, T. Hernandez-Boussard, E. Ho, M.-Y. Liu, T. McGrath, K. Powell, S. Pinglay,
943 D. P. Burke, H. Goodarzi, P. D. Hsu, B. L. Hie, Genome modelling and design across all
944 domains of life with Evo 2. *Nature*, 1–13 (2026).
- 945 86. D. H. Parks, P.-A. Chaumeil, A. J. Mussig, C. Rinke, M. Chuvochina, P. Hugenholtz,
946 GTDB release 10: a complete and systematic taxonomy for 715 230 bacterial and 17
947 245 archaeal genomes. *Nucleic Acids Research* **54**, D743–D754 (2026).
- 948 87. D. Paez-Espino, I.-M. A. Chen, K. Palaniappan, A. Ratner, K. Chu, E. Szeto, M. Pillay, J.
949 Huang, V. M. Markowitz, T. Nielsen, M. Huntemann, T. B. K. Reddy, G. A. Pavlopoulos,
950 M. B. Sullivan, B. J. Campbell, F. Chen, K. McMahan, S. J. Hallam, V. Deneff, R.
951 Cavicchioli, S. M. Caffrey, W. R. Streit, J. Webster, K. M. Handley, G. H. Salekdeh, N.
952 Tsesmetzis, J. C. Setubal, P. B. Pope, W.-T. Liu, A. R. Rivers, N. N. Ivanova, N. C.
953 Kyrpides, IMG/VR: a database of cultured and uncultured DNA Viruses and
954 retroviruses. *Nucleic Acids Research* **45**, gkw1030 (2016).
- 955 88. A. P. Camargo, L. Call, S. Roux, S. Nayfach, M. Huntemann, K. Palaniappan, A.
956 Ratner, K. Chu, S. Mukherjee, T. B. K. Reddy, I.-M. A. Chen, N. N. Ivanova, E. A. Eloe-
957 Fadrosch, T. Woyke, D. A. Baltrus, S. Castañeda-Barba, F. de la Cruz, B. E. Funnell, J. P.
958 J. Hall, A. Mukhopadhyay, E. P. C. Rocha, T. Stalder, E. Top, N. C. Kyrpides, IMG/PR: a
959 database of plasmids from genomes and metagenomes with rich annotations and
960 metadata. *Nucleic Acids Research* **52**, D164–D173 (2024).
- 961 89. H. Dalla-Torre, L. Gonzalez, J. Mendoza-Revilla, N. Lopez Carranza, A. H.
962 Grzywaczewski, F. Oteri, C. Dallago, E. Trop, B. P. de Almeida, H. Sirelkhatim, G.
963 Richard, M. Skwark, K. Beguir, M. Lopez, T. Pierrot, Nucleotide Transformer: building
964 and evaluating robust foundation models for human genomics. *Nat Methods* **22**,
965 287–297 (2025).

- 966 90. Y. Zeng, J. Xie, N. Shangguan, Z. Wei, W. Li, Y. Su, S. Yang, C. Zhang, J. Zhang, N. Fang,
967 H. Zhang, Y. Lu, H. Zhao, J. Fan, W. Yu, Y. Yang, CellFM: a large-scale foundation
968 model pre-trained on transcriptomics of 100 million human cells. *Nat Commun* **16**,
969 4679 (2025).
- 970 91. G. Heimberg, T. Kuo, D. J. DePianto, O. Salem, T. Heigl, N. Diamant, G. Scalia, T.
971 Biancalani, S. J. Turley, J. R. Rock, H. Corrada Bravo, J. Kaminker, J. A. Vander Heiden,
972 A. Regev, A cell atlas foundation model for scalable search of similar human cells.
973 *Nature* **638**, 1085–1094 (2025).
- 974 92. M. Hemberg, F. Marini, S. Ghazanfar, A. Al Ajami, N. Abassi, B. Anchang, B. A.
975 Benayoun, Y. Cao, K. Chen, Y. Cuesta-Astroz, Z. DeBruine, C. A. Dendrou, I. De
976 Vlaminck, K. Imkeller, I. Korsunsky, A. R. Lederer, J. J. Li, P. Meysman, C. L. Miller, K. A.
977 Mullan, U. Ohler, P. Panwar, N. Patikas, J. Schuck, J. H. Y. Siu, T. J. Triche, A. Tsankov,
978 S. W. van der Laan, M. Yajima, J. Yang, F. Zanini, I. Jelic, Insights, opportunities, and
979 challenges provided by large cell atlases. *Genome Biol* **26**, 358 (2025).
- 980 93. H. Feng, L. Wu, B. Zhao, C. Huff, J. Zhang, J. Wu, L. Lin, P. Wei, C. Wu, Benchmarking
981 DNA foundation models for genomic and genetic tasks. *Nat Commun* **16**, 10780
982 (2025).
- 983 94. R. Joeres, D. B. Blumenthal, O. V. Kalinina, Data splitting to avoid information leakage
984 with DataSAIL. *Nat Commun* **16**, 3337 (2025).
- 985 95. S. V. Nguyen, N. P. Puthuveetil, J. R. Petrone, J. L. Kirkland, K. Gaffney, C. L. Tabron, N.
986 Wax, J. Duncan, S. King, R. Marlow, A. L. Reese, D. A. Yarmosh, H. H. McConnell, A. S.
987 Fernandes, J. Bagnoli, B. Benton, J. L. Jacobs, The ATCC genome portal: 3,938
988 authenticated microbial reference genomes. *Microbiol Resour Announc* **13**, e01045-
989 23 (2024).
- 990 96. J. Barretina, G. Caponigro, N. Stransky, K. Venkatesan, A. A. Margolin, S. Kim, C. J.
991 Wilson, J. Lehár, G. V. Kryukov, D. Sonkin, A. Reddy, M. Liu, L. Murray, M. F. Berger, J. E.
992 Monahan, P. Morais, J. Meltzer, A. Korejwa, J. Jané-Valbuena, F. A. Mapa, J. Thibault, E.
993 Bric-Furlong, P. Raman, A. Shipway, I. H. Engels, J. Cheng, G. K. Yu, J. Yu, P. Aspesi, M.
994 De Silva, K. Jagtap, M. D. Jones, L. Wang, C. Hatton, E. Palesscandolo, S. Gupta, S.
995 Mahan, C. Sougnez, R. C. Onofrio, T. Liefeld, L. MacConaill, W. Winckler, M. Reich, N.
996 Li, J. P. Mesirov, S. B. Gabriel, G. Getz, K. Ardlie, V. Chan, V. E. Myer, B. L. Weber, J.
997 Porter, M. Warmuth, P. Finan, J. L. Harris, M. Meyerson, T. R. Golub, M. P. Morrissey,
998 W. R. Sellers, R. Schlegel, L. A. Garraway, The Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia enables
999 predictive modelling of anticancer drug sensitivity. *Nature* **483**, 603–607 (2012).
- 1000 97. B. Haibe-Kains, N. El-Hachem, N. J. Birkbak, A. C. Jin, A. H. Beck, H. J. W. L. Aerts, J.
1001 Quackenbush, Inconsistency in large pharmacogenomic studies. *Nature* **504**, 389–
1002 393 (2013).

- 1003 98. M. Bouhaddou, M. S. DiStefano, E. A. Riesel, E. Carrasco, H. Y. Holzapfel, D. C. Jones,
1004 G. R. Smith, A. D. Stern, S. S. Somani, T. V. Thompson, M. R. Birtwistle, Drug response
1005 consistency in CCLE and CGP. *Nature* **540**, E9–E10 (2016).
- 1006 99. J. P. Mpindi, B. Yadav, P. Östling, P. Gautam, D. Malani, A. Murumägi, A. Hirasawa, S.
1007 Kangaspeska, K. Wennerberg, O. Kallioniemi, T. Aittokallio, Consistency in drug
1008 response profiling. *Nature* **540**, E5–E6 (2016).
- 1009 100. U. Ben-David, B. Siranosian, G. Ha, H. Tang, Y. Oren, K. Hinohara, C. A. Strathdee, J.
1010 Dempster, N. J. Lyons, R. Burns, A. Nag, G. Kugener, B. Cimini, P. Tsvetkov, Y. E.
1011 Maruvka, R. O'Rourke, A. Garrity, A. A. Tubelli, P. Bandopadhyay, A. Tsherniak, F.
1012 Vazquez, B. Wong, C. Birger, M. Ghandi, A. R. Thorner, J. A. Bittker, M. Meyerson, G.
1013 Getz, R. Beroukhim, T. R. Golub, Genetic and transcriptional evolution alters cancer
1014 cell line drug response. *Nature* **560**, 325–330 (2018).
- 1015 101. R. E. Hynds, E. Vladimirov, Sam. M. Janes, The secret lives of cancer cell lines.
1016 *Disease Models & Mechanisms* **11**, dmm037366 (2018).
- 1017 102. H. Sichtig, T. Minogue, Y. Yan, C. Stefan, A. Hall, L. Tallon, L. Sadzewicz, S. Nadendla,
1018 W. Klimke, E. Hatcher, M. Shumway, D. L. Aldea, J. Allen, J. Koehler, T. Slezak, S.
1019 Lovell, R. Schoepp, U. Scherf, FDA-ARGOS is a database with public quality-
1020 controlled reference genomes for diagnostic use and regulatory science. *Nat*
1021 *Commun* **10**, 3313 (2019).
- 1022 103. J. Dicks, M.-A. Fazal, K. Oliver, N. E. Grayson, J. D. Turnbull, E. Bane, E. Burnett, A.
1023 Deheer-Graham, N. Holroyd, D. Kaushal, J. Keane, G. Langridge, J. Lomax, H.
1024 McGregor, S. Picton, M. Quail, D. Singh, A. Tracey, J. Korlach, J. E. Russell, S.
1025 Alexander, J. Parkhill, NCTC3000: a century of bacterial strain collecting leads to a
1026 rich genomic data resource. *Microbial Genomics* **9** (2023).
- 1027 104. S. Kato, S. Masuda, A. Shibata, T. Itoh, M. Sakamoto, K. Shirasu, M. Ohkuma, Whole-
1028 genome sequencing of diverse 351 cultured prokaryotes including as-yet-
1029 unsequenced type strains. *Genome Res* **36**, 875–884 (2026).
- 1030 105. L. Wu, K. McCluskey, P. Desmeth, S. Liu, S. Hideaki, Y. Yin, O. Moriya, T. Itoh, C. Y.
1031 Kim, J.-S. Lee, Y. Zhou, H. Kawasaki, M. H. Hazbón, V. Robert, T. Boekhout, N. Lima, L.
1032 Evtushenko, K. Boundy-Mills, B. Bunk, E. R. B. Moore, L. Eurwilaichitr, S. Ingsriswang,
1033 H. Shah, S. Yao, T. Jin, J. Huang, W. Shi, Q. Sun, G. Fan, W. Li, X. Li, İ. Kurtböke, J. Ma,
1034 The global catalogue of microorganisms 10K type strain sequencing project: closing
1035 the genomic gaps for the validly published prokaryotic and fungi species.
1036 *GigaScience* **7** (2018).
- 1037 106. P. S. G. Chain, D. V. Grafham, R. S. Fulton, M. G. FitzGerald, J. Hostetler, D. Muzny, J.
1038 Ali, B. Birren, D. C. Bruce, C. Buhay, J. R. Cole, Y. Ding, S. Dugan, D. Field, G. M.
1039 Garrity, R. Gibbs, T. Graves, C. S. Han, S. H. Harrison, S. Highlander, P. Hugenholtz, H.

- 1040 M. Khouri, C. D. Kodira, E. Kolker, N. C. Kyrpides, D. Lang, A. Lapidus, S. A. Malfatti, V.
1041 Markowitz, T. Metha, K. E. Nelson, J. Parkhill, S. Pitluck, X. Qin, T. D. Read, J. Schmutz,
1042 S. Sozhamannan, P. Sterk, R. L. Strausberg, G. Sutton, N. R. Thomson, J. M. Tiedje, G.
1043 Weinstock, A. Wollam, Genomic Standards Consortium Human Microbiome Project
1044 Jumpstart Consortium, J. C. Detter, Genome Project Standards in a New Era of
1045 Sequencing. *Science* **326**, 236–237 (2009).
- 1046 107. J. Wieczorek, D. Bloom, R. Guralnick, S. Blum, M. Döring, R. Giovanni, T. Robertson,
1047 D. Vieglais, Darwin Core: An Evolving Community-Developed Biodiversity Data
1048 Standard. *PLoS ONE* **7**, e29715 (2012).
- 1049 108. G. Droege, K. Barker, O. Seberg, J. Coddington, E. Benson, W. G. Berendsohn, B.
1050 Bunk, C. Butler, E. M. Cawsey, J. Deck, M. Döring, P. Flemons, B. Gemeinholzer, A.
1051 Güntsch, T. Hollowell, P. Kelbert, I. Kostadinov, R. Kottmann, R. T. Lawlor, C. Lyal, J.
1052 Mackenzie-Dodds, C. Meyer, D. Mulcahy, S. Y. Nussbeck, É. O’Tuama, T. Orrell, G.
1053 Petersen, T. Robertson, C. Söhngen, J. Whitacre, J. Wieczorek, P. Yilmaz, H. Zetzsche,
1054 Y. Zhang, X. Zhou, The Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) Data Standard
1055 specification. *Database* **2016**, baw125 (2016).
- 1056 109. E. J. Griffiths, R. E. Timme, A. J. Page, N.-F. Alikhan, D. Fornika, F. Maguire, C. I.
1057 Mendes, S. H. Tausch, A. Black, T. R. Connor, G. H. Tyson, D. M. Aanensen, B. Alcock,
1058 J. Campos, A. Christoffels, A. Gonçalves Da Silva, E. Hodcroft, W. W. L. Hsiao, L. S.
1059 Katz, S. M. Nicholls, P. E. Oluniyi, I. B. Olawoye, A. R. Raphenya, A. T. R. Vasconcelos,
1060 A. A. Witney, D. R. MacCannell, The PHA4GE SARS-CoV-2 Contextual Data
1061 Specification for Open Genomic Epidemiology. *Biology and Life Sciences [Preprint]*
1062 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202008.0220.v1>.
- 1063 110. E. J. Griffiths, R. E. Timme, C. I. Mendes, A. J. Page, N.-F. Alikhan, D. Fornika, F.
1064 Maguire, J. Campos, D. Park, I. B. Olawoye, P. E. Oluniyi, D. Anderson, A. Christoffels,
1065 A. G. da Silva, R. Cameron, D. Dooley, L. S. Katz, A. Black, I. Karsch-Mizrachi, T.
1066 Barrett, A. Johnston, T. R. Connor, S. M. Nicholls, A. A. Witney, G. H. Tyson, S. H.
1067 Tausch, A. R. Raphenya, B. Alcock, D. M. Aanensen, E. Hodcroft, W. W. L. Hsiao, A. T.
1068 R. Vasconcelos, D. R. MacCannell, Future-proofing and maximizing the utility of
1069 metadata: The PHA4GE SARS-CoV-2 contextual data specification package.
1070 *GigaScience* **11**, giac003 (2022).
- 1071 111. A. Klie, B. Y. Tsui, S. Mollah, D. Skola, M. Dow, C.-N. Hsu, H. Carter, Increasing
1072 metadata coverage of SRA BioSample entries using deep learning–based named
1073 entity recognition. *Database (Oxford)* **2021**, baab021 (2021).
- 1074 112. V. Simonyan, J. Goecks, R. Mazumder, Biocompute Objects—A Step towards
1075 Evaluation and Validation of Biomedical Scientific Computations. *PDA Journal of*
1076 *Pharmaceutical Science and Technology* **71**, 136–146 (2017).

- 1077 113. Food and Drug Administration, Electronic Submissions; Data Standards; Support for
1078 the International Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Bioinformatics
1079 Computations and Analyses Standard for Bioinformatic Workflows (2020).
1080 <https://www.federalregister.gov/d/2020-15771>.
- 1081 114. P. W. Harrison, J. Fan, D. Richardson, L. Clarke, D. Zerbino, G. Cochrane, A. L.
1082 Archibald, C. J. Schmidt, P. Flicek, FAANG , establishing metadata standards,
1083 validation and best practices for the farmed and companion animal community.
1084 *Animal Genetics* **49**, 520–526 (2018).
- 1085 115. ENCODE Project Consortium, An integrated encyclopedia of DNA elements in the
1086 human genome. *Nature* **489**, 57–74 (2012).

1087 Acknowledgements

1088 Sincere thanks is given to colleagues who reviewed this manuscript prior to publication,
1089 including Cara Wilder, David Yarmosh, Emily White, Scott Nguyen, David Molik, Sterling
1090 Sawaya, James Crill, Patrick Boyle, and Ruth Cheng.

1091 **Funding:** This work was supported by internal funding from ATCC.

1092 **Author Contributions:** The conceptualization, investigation, and writing of this manuscript
1093 was done by J.L.J.

1094 **Competing Interests:** The author declares no competing interests.

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